

AA Nanopore

Content

- [Description](#)
- [Requirments](#)
 - [Data Requirements](#)
 - [Hardware Requirements](#)
 - [Software Requirements](#)
- [Installation](#)
- [Examples](#)
 - [Step1: Read and polish the raw current signal](#)
 - [Step2 \(optional\): Identify the base line \(L0\) and blockade signal \(L1\) of amino acids signals](#)
 - [Step3: Extract signal events from original signals](#)
 - [Step4: Extract features of signal events for classifier training or amino acid prediction](#)
 - [Step5: Predict amino acid](#)
- [License](#)
- [References](#)

Description

`AANanopore` is an open source R package for the signal processing, feature extraction, and prediction of amino acids nanopore signals. The original input file is .ABF file containing the current value of amino acids nanopore signals collected by Clampex software. In this package, the functions `CurrentPolish`, `LevelIdentify`, `SignalExtract`, `FeatureExtract`, and `Predict` can be used to process and predict the signals.

Requirments

Data Requirements

If you want to run this R package successfully, you may need a ABF file and a classification model. Because the raw ABF file is too large for GitHub, we uploaded one of raw ABF file `21306010.abf` to [figshare](#). User can download the `21306010.abf` file from [figshare](#) by [10.6084/m9.figshare.21385695](#). For this manul, we also uploaded a trained random forest classifier to [figshare](#). User can also download the `RF_model.Rds` file from [figshare](#) by [10.6084/m9.figshare.21385722](#).

Hardware Requirements

The `AANanopore` package requires only a standard computer with enough RAM to support the operations defined by a user. For minimal performance, this will be a computer with about 2 GB of RAM. For optimal performance, we recommend a computer with the following specs:

- RAM: 16+ GB
- CPU: 4+ cores, 3.3+ GHz/core

Software Requirements

The package development version is tested on *Linux* operating systems. Before setting up the `AANanopore` package, users should have `R` version 4.0.0 or higher, and several packages set up from CRAN.

Users should install the following packages prior to installing `AANanopore`, from an `R` terminal:

```
install.packages(c("changepoint", "readABF", "testthat", "S4Vectors",  
"IRanges", "plotly", "ggplot2", "data.table", "crosstalk"))
```

Installation

First, we need to install `devtools`:

```
install.packages("devtools")  
library(devtools)
```

Then we just call

```
install_github("LuChenLab/AANanoporeR")  
library(AANanopore)
```

Examples

Step1: Read and polish the raw current signal

First, we need to read and polish the raw current signal from the ABF file using `CurrentPolish` function:

```
library(AANanopore)  
library(data.table)  
library(ggplot2)  
File <- file.path("/File/Path/To/ABF/File")  
abf <- CurrentPolish(file = File, TimeStart = 0, TimeEnd = 0)
```

Step2 (optional): Identify the base line (L0) and blockade signal (L1) of amino acids signals

If the range of L0 (base line) and L1 (blockade signal) of ABF file is unknown, the function `LevelIdentify` can be used to identify:

```
L01 <- LevelIdentify(object = abf, L0Min = NA, L0Max = NA, L1Min =  
NA, L1Max = NA)
```

```
> L01 <- AANanopore::LevelIdentify(object = mat)
[1] "We need identify the baseline from data."
The adjust: 0.5
The minimum of baseline(pA): 111.8
The maximum of baseline(pA): 116
Continue? (Yes/no/cancel) Yes
[1] "Now, we need identify the L1 from data."
The theoretical value is OK?

1: YES
2: NO
```

```
Selection: 2
The minimum of L1(pA): 85.6
The maximum of L1(pA): 90.1
```


Step3: Extract signal events from original signals

After identify the signal level of ABF file, we can use `SignalExtract` function to extract the signal events:

```
BUBs <- SignalExtract(object = abf, L0Min = L01$L0Min, L0Max =
L01$L0Max, L1Min = L01$L1Min, L1Max = L01$L1Max)
```

Here, the object `BUBs` is a R list with signal events. Extracted signal can be illustrate by function `SigPlot`, the read line indicating the polished value of current signal.

```
SigPlot(x = BUBs[[1]])
```


#	X053	X054	X055	X056	X057	X058	X059	X060	X061	X062
	X063	X064	X065							
#	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000						
#	X066	X067	X068	X069	X070	X071	X072	X073	X074	X075
	X076	X077	X078							
#	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000						
#	X079	X080	X081	X082	X083	X084	X085	X086	X087	X088
	X089	X090	X091							
#	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000						
#	X092	X093	X094	X095	X096	X097	X098	X099	X100	X101
	X102	X103	X104							
#	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000						
#	X105	X106	X107	X108	X109	X110	X111	X112	X113	X114
	X115	X116	X117							
#	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.004	0.027	0.126	0.391	
	0.903	1.631	2.552	3.795						
#	X118	X119	X120	X121	X122	X123	X124	X125	X126	X127
	X128	X129	X130							
#	5.592	8.136	10.919	12.971	14.019	14.458	14.278	13.147	11.238	
	9.360	7.914	6.689	5.488						
#	X131	X132	X133	X134	X135	X136	X137	X138	X139	X140
	X141	X142	X143							
#	4.428	3.657	3.126	2.664	2.203	1.767	1.398	1.085	0.794	
	0.536	0.352	0.260	0.229						
#	X144	X145	X146	X147	X148	X149	X150	X151	X152	X153
	X154	X155	X156							
#	0.228	0.252	0.324	0.444	0.569	0.691	0.916	1.445	2.448	
	3.871	5.230	5.694	4.759						
#	X157	X158	X159	X160	X161	X162	X163	X164	X165	X166
	X167	X168	X169							
#	3.063	1.553	0.655	0.248	0.116	0.086	0.079	0.063	0.049	
	0.046	0.045	0.042	0.040						
#	X170	X171	X172	X173	X174	X175	X176	X177	X178	X179
	X180	X181	X182							

```

# 0.038 0.031 0.019 0.008 0.002 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000
0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000
# X183 X184 X185 X186 X187 X188 X189 X190 X191 X192
X193 X194 X195
# 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000
0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000
# X196 X197 X198 X199 X200
# 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000 0.000
# attr(,"AllTime")
# [1] 27.07
# attr(,"DwellTime")
# [1] 17.66
# attr(,"SignalSD")
# [1] 0.04052126
# attr(,"Blockade")
# [1] 0.378391

```

Step5: Predict amino acid

The signal event features of known amino acids can be used to train classifier or used to predict the amino acid type of new signal event. Here, we used our pre-trained random forest classifier to predict the **Fi**.

```

# Load the pre-trained random forest classifier
model <- readRDS("/Path/to/RF_model.Rds")
model
# Random Forest
#
# 81220 samples
# 204 predictor
# 20 classes: 'A', 'C', 'D', 'E', 'F', 'G', 'H', 'I', 'K', 'L', 'M',
'N', 'P', 'Q', 'R', 'S', 'T', 'V', 'W', 'Y'
#
# Pre-processing: centered (54), scaled (54), Yeo-Johnson
transformation (54), remove (150)
# Resampling: Cross-Validated (10 fold, repeated 10 times)
# Summary of sample sizes: 73099, 73100, 73098, 73099, 73098, 73099,
...

```

```

# Resampling results:
#
#   Accuracy   Kappa
# 0.8923492  0.8866833
#
# Tuning parameter 'mtry' was held constant at a value of 60

Preds <- lapply(Feats, function(x) AANanopore::Predict(x = x, model =
model))
Preds <- as.data.table(do.call(rbind, Preds))
Preds[1, ]
#   A      C D E F G H I      K L M N P      Q R S T V      W Y
# 1: 0 0.024 0 0 0 0 0 0 0.002 0 0 0 0 0.004 0 0 0 0 0.97 0

```

The result indicating that according our random forest classifier this signal event is W, and the probability is 0.97.

```

ggplot(melt.data.table(Preds), aes(x = variable, y = value)) +
  geom_boxplot(outlier.color = NA) +
  labs(x = "Amino acid", y = "Prediction probability") +
  theme_bw(base_size = 15)

```



```

Ans <- data.table(Prob = apply(Preds, 1, max), AA = colnames(Preds)
[apply(Preds, 1, which.max)])
Ans[, .N, AA][order(N, decreasing = T)]
#      AA    N
# 1:    W  870
# 2:    C  201
# 3:    F   79
# 4:    G   37
# 5:    Y   23
# 6:    D   16
# 7:    Q   12
# 8:    I   11
# 9:    R   10
#10:    E   10
#11:    V    9
#12:    N    9
#13:    S    9
#14:    H    8
#15:    P    7
#16:    A    6

```

```

# 17:  L   6
# 18:  K   5
# 19:  M   3
Ans[Prob > 0.7, .N, AA][order(N, decreasing = T)]
#   AA   N
# 1:  W 709
# 2:  C  24
# 3:  F   6
# 4:  E   1
# 5:  I   1
# 6:  Y   1
# 7:  G   1
# 8:  H   1

```

This results indicating that most of signal event are predicted as W.

Supplementary

The random forest classifier was trained using R package `caret`. And we used K-fold cross-validation to prevent overfitting of the modeling.

```

library(caret)
library(doParallel)
fitControl <- trainControl(method = "repeatedcv",
                           number = 10,
                           repeats = 10)

cl <- makePSOCKcluster(10)
registerDoParallel(cl)
model <- train(Class ~ .,
              data = Train,
              preProc = c("center", "scale", "YeoJohnson", "nzv"),
              method = "rf",
              trControl = fitControl,
              verbose = FALSE,
              ## to evaluate:
              tuneGrid = expand.grid(mtry = 60),
              # tuneLength = 50,

```

```
metric = "Accuracy",  
allowParallel = TRUE)
```

```
sessionInfo()  
# R version 4.0.2 (2020-06-22)  
# Platform: x86_64-pc-linux-gnu (64-bit)  
# Running under: Ubuntu 18.04.5 LTS  
#  
# Matrix products: default  
# BLAS: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/openblas/libblas.so.3  
# LAPACK: /usr/lib/x86_64-linux-gnu/libopenblas-p-r0.2.20.so  
#  
# locale:  
# [1] LC_CTYPE=en_US.UTF-8 LC_NUMERIC=C  
LC_TIME=en_US.UTF-8  
# [4] LC_COLLATE=en_US.UTF-8 LC_MONETARY=en_US.UTF-8  
LC_MESSAGES=en_US.UTF-8  
# [7] LC_PAPER=en_US.UTF-8 LC_NAME=C  
LC_ADDRESS=C  
# [10] LC_TELEPHONE=C LC_MEASUREMENT=en_US.UTF-8  
LC_IDENTIFICATION=C  
#  
# attached base packages:  
# [1] stats graphics grDevices utils datasets methods  
base  
#  
# other attached packages:  
# [1] ggplot2_3.3.2 data.table_1.13.0 AANanopore_0.1.0  
#  
# loaded via a namespace (and not attached):  
# [1] httr_1.4.2 tidyr_1.1.1 splines_4.0.2  
jsonlite_1.7.1  
# [5] viridisLite_0.3.0 foreach_1.5.0 proclim_2019.11.13  
shiny_1.5.0  
# [9] stats4_4.0.2 yaml_2.2.1 ipred_0.9-9  
pillar_1.4.6  
# [13] lattice_0.20-41 glue_1.4.1 pROC_1.16.2  
digest_0.6.25
```

```
# [17] XVector_0.28.0      RColorBrewer_1.1-2  promises_1.1.1
randomForest_4.6-14
# [21] colorspace_1.4-1    recipes_0.1.13      cowplot_1.0.0
htmltools_0.5.0
# [25] httpuv_1.5.4        Matrix_1.5-1        plyr_1.8.6
timeDate_3043.102
# [29] pkgconfig_2.0.3     caret_6.0-86        zlibbioc_1.34.0
purrr_0.3.4
# [33] xtable_1.8-4        scales_1.1.1        openxlsx_4.1.5
later_1.1.0.1
# [37] gower_0.2.2         lava_1.6.7          readABF_1.0.2
tibble_3.0.3
# [41] generics_0.0.2     farver_2.0.3        IRanges_2.22.2
ellipsis_0.3.1
# [45] withr_2.2.0         nnet_7.3-14         BiocGenerics_0.34.0
lazyeval_0.2.2
# [49] survival_3.2-3     magrittr_1.5        crayon_1.3.4
mime_0.9
# [53] MASS_7.3-51.6      nlme_3.1-148        changepoint_2.2.2
class_7.3-17
# [57] tools_4.0.2         lifecycle_0.2.0     stringr_1.4.0
plotly_4.9.2.1
# [61] S4Vectors_0.26.1   munsell_0.5.0       zip_2.0.4
Biostrings_2.56.0
# [65] compiler_4.0.2     tinytex_0.25        rlang_0.4.7
grid_4.0.2
# [69] iterators_1.0.12   rstudioapi_0.11     htmlwidgets_1.5.1
crosstalk_1.1.0.1
# [73] labeling_0.3        testthat_2.3.2      ModelMetrics_1.2.2.2
gtable_0.3.0
# [77] codetools_0.2-16   reshape2_1.4.4      R6_2.4.1
lubridate_1.7.9
# [81] zoo_1.8-8           dplyr_1.0.1         fastmap_1.0.1
stringi_1.4.6
# [85] parallel_4.0.2     Rcpp_1.0.7          rpart_4.1-15
vctrs_0.3.2
# [89] tidyselect_1.1.0   xfun_0.16
```

License

This project is covered under the **GPL License**.

References